

RADx-UP BACKGROUND

The National Institutes of Health (NIH)-supported [Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics-Underserved Populations \(RADx-UP\) Program](#) funds projects across the US, its territories, and Tribal Nations to address COVID-19 testing disparities. RADx-UP projects use various community engagement (CE) models, frameworks, and principles to increase COVID-19 testing access and pandemic preparedness among underserved communities. The Tracking and Evaluation Team (T&E) at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill (UNC) oversees the RADx-UP evaluation. As part of a larger, mixed-methods evaluation, T&E developed a qualitative evaluation plan (QEP) for RADx-UP.

QUALITATIVE EVALUATION

The T&E team conducted the qualitative evaluation using the [Translational Science Benefits Model \(TSBM\)](#) to assess RADx-UP projects' clinical accomplishments, community benefits, and policy implications and the [Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance \(RE-AIM\) model](#) to investigate projects' perceptions of their reach, implementation strategies, and maintenance (or sustainability).

[Click here for more information about how T&E uses these models to evaluate RADx-UP \(see page 2\).](#)

EVALUATION QUESTIONS

1

COVID-19 Testing Determinants, Outcomes, Impacts, and Learning

- To what extent have the RADx-UP projects achieved their aims, goals, outcomes, and sustained impacts?

2

Community Engagement and Community-Academic Partnerships

- What was the extent of projects' community engagement activities and community-academic partnerships in RADx-UP?
- How did these activities and partnerships influence projects' ability to achieve outcomes and sustained impacts?

3

Community Health and Equity

- What general conclusions can be drawn about improving community health, through increased access to COVID-19 testing, and health equity through a RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) program approach?

METHODS AND SAMPLE

Interviews

T&E sampled 13 diverse projects and conducted 24 individual 45-minute interviews by Zoom

13 Academic Partners

11 Community Partners

serving

13 RADx-UP Communities

Black

Rural

American Indian

Youth

Pacific Islander

LGBTQ+

Hispanic/Latino/Latinx

Low SES

Immigrant and Refugee

Children with intellectual and developmental disabilities

Underrepresented Populations in Communities

RESULTS

Qualitative interviews revealed the following findings in relation to our evaluation questions :

- 1** **RADx-UP projects generally felt they successfully achieved their aims** (reaching underserved populations with COVID-19 testing); however, the dynamic and crisis nature of COVID-19, coupled with administrative burdens, created implementation and maintenance challenges.
- 2** **Community partnerships were seen as foundational to the projects' efforts.** Specifically, the partnerships strengthened public health preparedness and capacity. They resulted in multi-dimensional benefits, including increased clinical services, improved ability to address social determinants of health, and improved adoption of local COVID-19 mitigation policies.
- 3** **The RADx-UP approach was generally viewed as effective in supporting testing and addressing health equity;** however, additional resources and continued relationship building were indicated as required to maintain community-academic partnerships and their ability to address health equity among underserved populations.

PHOTO COURTESY RADx-UP IMAGE

RADx-UP TSBM PROJECT BENEFITS

Clinical Benefits

- Increased COVID-19 diagnostic and preventative health services.

“We were able to increase testing in communities we serve in collaboration with [our community partner] and developed and provided COVID-19 informational resources to the community, increased access to home testing, and increased access to timely testing as well”

– Academic Partner.

Policy Benefits

- Increased advocacy for communities.
- Research findings resulted in local COVID-19 mitigation policies.

“This [project] helped us shape our internal—our COVID-19 mitigation policies and things like that and how we did our COVID screenings and different things in office”

– Community Partner

Community Benefits

- Increased health equity by addressing social determinants of health, such as health insurance, transportation, food, water, and cellular connectivity.

“[Our protocol included] asking [families] if they’ve had any social determinants of health issues, so whether it’s been loss of income, not familiar with a resource, they’re in need of a food pantry, or just any other resource in the community, and if they need help with them, it prompts them to select yes or no on if they want to be connected with a family navigator who then would help them meet their need”

– Academic Partner

- Increased access to health services through transportation, flexible scheduling, and accessible locations.
- Increased culturally tailored public health information on COVID-19.

COMMUNITY-ACADEMIC PARTNERSHIPS STRENGTHENED PUBLIC HEALTH PREPAREDNESS AND CAPACITY

Partnerships increased preparedness in communities.

“We have partnerships with the neighborhoods where we may have to dispatch and set up another pop-up testing site. We have those partnerships already built, and it won’t take much to initiate them again if we need to. I think we’re prepared for any kind of emergency.”

–Community Partner

CBPR approach built trust between research teams, community partners, and community members.

“I highly recommend building and strengthening community partnerships and trust within communities, it is essential. It allows for more capacity for quality healthcare for the community. ”

–Academic Partner

Academic-community partnerships increased capacity for research in communities through shared staff, infrastructure, and training.

“We’ve had kind of like good sessions on from capacity building for research. We had, like a specialist, help us with the training process that had a large component about just explaining the whole research process, why is it important.”

–Academic Partner

“One of the things I think that contributed to our overall success is having people from the community who are already trusted involved.”

– Community Partner

RE-AIM SUCCESSES, CHALLENGES, AND LESSONS LEARNED TO PROMOTE HEALTH EQUITY

	Successes	Challenges	Lessons Learned
Reach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recruitment through in-person and social media outreach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recruitment with limited study eligibility, technology challenges, COVID-19 fatigue, and misinformation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To improve community health, projects need to engage community members and partners to determine the best outreach strategies
Effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased health equity by increasing COVID-19 testing and resources, and addressing social determinants of health in communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obtaining COVID-19 tests or equipment in times of supply shortages Obtaining COVID-19 tests or equipment in times of supply shortages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obtaining COVID-19 tests or equipment in times of supply shortages
Adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting local and organizational mitigation policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lacking staff and/or infrastructure to adopt implementation in certain sites Capacity to implement amidst a public health crisis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CDCC can help projects facilitate ways to increase adoption at organizational, local, state, and national levels
Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community-informed implementation Community advisory boards provide input and feedback on research strategies Representation of community on research teams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grant administrative burdens, such as common data elements (CDEs) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public health requires adaptable and flexible implementation strategies and administration and operational procedures. CDCC can facilitate more networking opportunities to help projects share best practices for implementing interventions to improve community health
Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some RADx-UP projects have secured additional funding to continue COVID-19 project activities in communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Securing additional funding is a challenge but necessary for sustained research activities in underserved communities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As concern over COVID-19 diminishes, community and academic partners must shift focus to other community needs to maintain efforts to improve health equity

RECOMMENDATIONS

Continue to promote cross-project resource sharing and lessons learned. Activate more work groups, project-wide meetings, and project-led workshops.

Offer more dissemination support to projects. Help projects with creating and distributing research findings dissemination products, consider- what, how, where, when, and who.

Provide facilitated discussions on sustainability to project partners. For example, RADx-UP could help to support plans and next steps for maintenance and sustainability.

Offer increased support to help projects navigate grant and data requirements to lessen the burden so project can focus on implementation and funding goals.

[CLICK HERE to read the full report.](#)

FOR MORE INFORMATION
ABOUT THE RADx-UP EVALUATION, PLEASE VISIT:

[RADX-UP.ORG](https://radx-up.org)

